

D4.7 – BIMprove Asset Portfolio

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D4.7 – BIMprove Asset Portfolio

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Contributing partners	All
Reviewer(s)	Gabor Sziebig (SINTEF)

Abstract

The deliverable presents a collection of exploitable results achieved by the project, which created impact during its lifetime and with the potential to contribute for further work, research or innovations. This includes all peer-reviewed and technical publications, source code repository, open research data, educational material, and standardisation/ open-source contributions.

Keywords

Exploitable results, publications, open-source repository

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	2023. August 6 th	Initial version	Dag Fjeld Edvardsen (CATENDA)
v0.2	2023. August 20 th	Review of Comments, Corrections	All
v1.0	2023. August 31 st	Approved, final version	Gabor Sziebig (SINTEF)

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BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. BIMprove homepage

The homepage could be accessed on the following URL:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/>

Figure 1 Screenshot from BIMprove homepage

2. Videos

All video content (total 31) created within the frame of BIMprove, can be accessed on the following URL:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/gallery/>

Figure 2 Screenshot from the gallery of BIMprove homepage

3. Articles

All descriptive articles (total 60) could be accessed on the following URL:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/activities/>

Figure 3 Screenshot from articles on BIMprove homepage

4. Standardization

One of the key exploitable results from BIMprove project is the CWA Document on markers. All related videos and documents could be accessed on the following URL:

<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/markers/>

Figure 4 Screenshot from standardization page on BIMprove homepage

5. Open Research Data Pilot

In BIMprove project an Open Research Data Pilot has been created.

The repository is currently hosted on Bitbucket on the following link: <https://bitbucket.org/sintef-manufacturing/openaccess/>

Figure 5 Screenshot from the repository hosted on Bitbucket

6. Reports, papers, deliverables and newsletters

All public deliverables, peer reviewed articles and content has also been published on the online repository of Zenodo. The community could be accessed with the following URL: https://zenodo.org/communities/bimprove_h2020/

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the BIMprove H2020 Project community. At the top, the Zenodo logo and navigation links (Search, Upload, Communities, Log in, Sign up) are visible. The main heading is "BIMprove H2020 Project". Below this, there is a "Recent uploads" section with a search bar and a "New upload" button. Three uploads are listed:

- August 29, 2023 (v1)** | Other | Open Access | View
Digital Building Twins Projects - Joint Flash Newsletter # 1
Mona Marill; Natalia Cediel; Agnieszka Mikołajczyk; Davide Quaggiotto; Carmen Serna;
ASHVIN, BIMProve, COGITO and BIM2TWIN present the project clusters' joint flash newsletter #1 of these four EU-supported research projects devoted to developing Digital Building Twin technologies to boost tomorrow's European construction industry! All these projects arrive at
Uploaded on August 29, 2023
- August 7, 2023 (v1)** | Other | Open Access | View
BIMprove 7th Newsletter
BIMprove Consortium;
BIMprove project is coming to an end and this is the last Newsletter. We are impressed about how much new has actually been created in the project and want to celebrate our results with you. Among other things, we have developed: - An interface where you can set up paths / routes for data
Uploaded on August 7, 2023
- June 30, 2023 (v1.0)** | Project deliverable | Open Access | View
D3.6–Benchmarking, Evaluation & Demonstration
Antonio López-Ríos; Chiara Zarna;
This deliverable document the installation process on site, observation of problems, errors and possible improvements as well as metric control for benchmark. The documentation process is carried out by all industrial partners, as final users of the result of this research project.
Uploaded on June 30, 2023

On the right side, a community profile for "BIMprove H2020 Project" is shown, featuring the BIMprove logo and the following information:

- Community**
- BIMprove H2020 Project**
- Open Access Repository to Project BIMprove H2020 Grant agreement ID: 958450
- BIMprove has the ambition to revolutionize the stagnant European construction industry and solve long-standing problems such as decreasing productivity, dangerous environment for workers, negative environmental impact and budget misalignment with real expenditures.
<https://www.bimprove-h2020.eu/>
- Curated by:** BIMprove_h2020
- Curation policy:** Only material related to BIMprove project
- Created:** February 24, 2021

Figure 6 Screenshot from the Zenodo repository BIMprove community